

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ZRAIBI****FIRST NAME: COLETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did not use Zotero to insert references
The author did not use Grammarly Premium
The author used the following software: MSWord 2008 on Windows 10

List of my 6 key concepts with page number in text (these terms are also bold in my RP):

1. Structure (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. US vs. UK English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
4. Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
5. Euclid Word template (EUCLID 2015)

INTRODUCTION TO SUCCESSFUL WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

At a doctorate level, research papers shall be structured and well written. In order to develop the author's abilities to write a successful research paper, the course called "ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1" (EUCLID 2019) introduces key concepts of international academic writing that lead to that success.

I could identify five key concepts for the author to adopt. These concepts allow to become a successful academic author, respecting the international academic writing rules.

2)CONCEPT 1: STRUCTURE

Any writing paper shall have a clear **structure** that will enable the reader to follow the author's flow of arguments. It shall include three separate parts: the introduction, the body and the conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). Additionally, the paper shall end with a references/bibliography section (EUCLID 2019, 10).

The content of the body contains the arguments that the author shall present to defend his/her theory (EUCLID 2019, 3). Therefore, a successful content can only be achieved when the student has undertaken a preliminary work on the task.

Writing a paper does not start at the moment of starting the writing of the paper. It starts with the reading and researching process. At this process, the student shall take notes, and save the potential references he/she might use, using Zotero for example.

In order to build the arguments, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the task and draw up an initial structure that may be amended with the reviews. In my opinion, having a structured paper is more beneficial for the author than the reader. It helps organizing the ideas to develop the correct arguments and find the proper responses for potential counterarguments. I personally find that a non-structured writing leads the reader to confusion and the loss of interest in the paper.

3) CONCEPT 2: PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that is defined as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). When writing the arguments, the author must use evidence to support them. How to use others’ information without being accused of **plagiarism**?

The answer is to properly cite the author of the source of information by using one of the two ways of citing:

- Using the in-text citation, or
- Using the List of Works Cited.

Each requires its own format that the author needs to follow, when citing.

a) In-text citation

The in-text citation refers most commonly to quotations and paraphrases. Where quotations shall refer to the “exact words of the author” (EUCLID 2019, 6), in the contrary, the paraphrases shall not refer to the exact words of the author (EUCLID 2019, 8).

I find that quotations are the easiest in-text citations to use. They can refer to a sentence from an author or to a section from a book. From a reader point of view, I think that they provide the exact reference on where to find the evidence of the argument. From an author point of view, it is easier to include in the writing paper, provided the section or the sentence has been previously highlighted during the preliminary reading and researching process.

b) List of Works Cited

The List of Works Cited refers to providing a list of the references at the end of the paper, with detailed information on the source of the information (book or website),

including the author's name, date, book title, website's Uniform Resource Locator (URL) etc. (EUCLID 2019, 10-11)

It is in this section that the author refers all the works cited in the paper.

It is worthy to highlight the importance of referencing and taking notes of the references during the reading and researching process in the preliminary work.

4) CONCEPT 3: AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

There are two versions of English: **the US vs. the UK English**. These two versions have several differences that cover a wide range of differences in the pronunciation, the spelling, the grammar, the punctuation, etc. (EUCLID 2019, 27-35).

It is very important for a non-native English speaker to make the difference between these two versions. However, I find it difficult to detect the difference when the author is a non-native English. Fortunately, tools exist to help the author read proofing in the correct English version. Personally, I use the language review tab in Microsoft Word, for all my papers. This provides a certain assurance for the author that the paper is English correct, and it avoids unnecessary mistakes in the paper.

Although both versions of English are accepted, research and technical papers use mostly the American English and EUCLID recommends using it as well (EUCLID 2019, 24). Therefore, I will use the American English.

5) CONCEPT 4: TURABIAN STYLE

Another concept that an author shall adopt when writing the research paper is the style. A style is a format standard that the author shall follow. There are several style guides available. However, the **Turabian style** is the style that provides the most comprehensive guidance to writing research papers. It is based on the Chicago style and it is the style that all authors of research papers follow (EUCLID 2019, 44).

The Turabian style covers the rules of the Chicago style, which can be divided into three parts:

1. The style and usage, covering the rules of abbreviations, the capitalization, the compound words, the emphasis: italics/quotes, the numbers & dates, and the quotations (EUCLID 2019, 44-49),
2. The page formatting, covering the title and text page, the footnotes, the headings & lists, the bibliography & tables, and the table notes (EUCLID 2019, 49-53),

3. The end/footnotes, covering the authors & books, the journal & newspapers, the reports & papers and the references & documents (EUCLID 2019, 53-55).

More details can be found in Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996.

6) CONCEPT 5: EUCLID WORD DOCUMENT TEMPLATE

At this stage of the course, the last important concept for writing a successful paper is to adopt the **EUCLID Word response paper template**.

A study material available in the format of video shows how to personalize the template. It also demonstrates how to use the referencing tools, the style tools, and the language proofing amongst other features.

I have found the use of the template practical. It has the benefits of a pre-approved style. I also found the video helpful in understanding the purpose of the course, and in identifying its concepts.

7) CONCLUSION

The purpose of the course is to teach how to achieve a successful writing paper that respects the international academic writing rules. Five concepts were identified as key to adopt in writing. If the author creates a clear structure, avoids plagiarism, chooses the American English version and adopts the Turabian's style within the EUCLID template, then the author has a solid basis to write a successful paper.

LIST OF WORKS CITED

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.